

Prevalence of Metabolic Syndrome and its components in semi-urban Bali and urban Bamenda Health districts, North West Region of Cameroon: Strategies for mitigation

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Abstract

Background: Metabolic syndrome (MS) has been determined in forest regions of Cameroon, but not in the North West region which is culturally and geographically distinct from the south.

Objective: The objective was to determine the prevalence of metabolic syndrome and its components in the Bali (semi-urban area) and Bamenda (urban area) health districts of the North West Region of Cameroon. **Methods:** The study targeted the adult population aged 18-89 years old living within the Bamenda and Bali Health Districts as well as healthcare personnel in the two districts. Biochemical parameters of driving factors of MS were determined using standard methods. An interview guide (questionnaire) was used to assess the views of the population and healthcare personnel on the management and prevention of MS. The data collected were analysed using SPSS version 21. The results were presented in the form of tables and charts. **Results:** Bamenda Health District had a higher prevalence (48.65%) compared to Bali Health District (43.90%). The difference in prevalence between the two Health Districts was not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). The components of MS had the following prevalence; Obesity (51.3%), High blood pressure (70.9%), High blood glucose (66%), High Triglycerides (14.6%), Low HDL-C (26.9%) and waist circumference (98.31cm). **Conclusion:** It is essential to implement routine screening for risk factors associated with metabolic syndrome, alongside promoting healthy lifestyles and providing nutritional counselling in health units. Increasing public awareness about the management and prevention of metabolic syndrome components is crucial. Emphasizing the importance of regular exercise and a balanced diet can help prevent the progression of metabolic syndrome to more severe conditions, such as cardiovascular disease and diabetes.

Key words: Prevalence, metabolic syndrome, hypertension, obesity, Triglycerides, semi-urban, urban Bali, Bamenda health district, Cameroon

Introduction

Metabolic syndrome is widespread among adults from North America, Europe and Asia, and several reports of its prevalence in various populations have been published in recent years [1-2], most of them in developed countries. According to WHO (2011) [3] 30% to 50% of death were attributed to hypertension in developing countries. The prevalence of MS in Africa ranges from 0% to 50% or even higher depending on the population studied and the criteria used in defining it [4]. The prevalence of MS was found to be 35.1% (ATP III) in North-Western Nigeria, 21.8% (IDF) in adults in South Africa attending healthcare facilities in Eastern Cape, 35.73% (IDF) among adults in Morocco, 25.6% among urban Kenyan population, and 38.98% (IDF) in adult men in the Dschang Health District in the west region of Cameroon [5, 6, 7, 8, 9].

In Cameroon, the scientific literature does not have sufficient data to establish the national prevalence of MS. Cameroon is a low-income country [10], severely affected by the cardio-metabolic diseases [11]. The result is an increase of stroke (24% deaths per year), myocardial infarction (18% deaths per year), diabetes (10% of deaths per year) and hypertension affecting 35% of the adult population [12]. It is at the average age of 30 that young people gain salaried employment in Cameroon and retire at around 60 years old [12]. According to United Nations Program of Development, entry into the active life is related to regular financial accessibility particularly in Cameroon. This leads very often to the rapid acquisition of harmful lifestyles linked to changes in diet and physical activity patterns [11].

A study on metabolic syndrome among Cameroonians in the Dschang Health District showed a prevalence of 38.98%, with 48.6% and 31.97% respectively in urban and rural areas, related to the increase of the risks of the cardiometabolic diseases. The findings suggest that the poor lifestyle, physical inactivity, tobacco consumption, alcoholism, low educational level and poor eating habits were associated with the high prevalence of metabolic syndrome [12]. The IDF definition of metabolic syndrome gave a prevalence rate of 8.4%. Prevalence of central obesity and diastolic hypertension were highest. Background indicators, lifestyle options, family history and determinants) explained roughly 86.7% of the variability of Metabolic Syndrome [13].

The prevalence of MS was 44.77% and was decreasing with aging among Bamileke ethnic women Yaoundé, Cameroon; the younger adult women were more affected. Low HDL-cholesterol (79.85%) and high abdominal (64.17%) obesity level are respectively the most

frequent characteristics in comparison to other metabolic components [14]. The prevalence of metabolic syndrome among Mbo women in Yaoundé was 3.03%. High blood pressure level was 43.93% and high fasting glucose 14.39% were respectively the most frequent characteristics in comparison to other metabolic components [15]. In Dschang health district, Western Region of Cameroon, the prevalence of MS in pregnant women was 17.88% (95% CI: 15.03–21.14) majorly determined by pre-gestational obesity [16]. In another study on adult males and females, in the Bamoutos Division, West Region of Cameroon, the prevalence of MS was 32.45% with highly significant female predominance (46.11% for females and 14.01% for males). In that study, most common abnormalities were low HDL (82.78%) and hypertriglyceridemia (53.97%) had a higher risk of developing MS [17].

Materials and methods

Study design

A population-based cross-sectional survey was performed from July 2022 to June 2023 among adult urban population of Bamenda and semi-urban population of Bali, North-West Region of Cameroon.

Study site

The study area was the grass field area of Cameroon, Bali (Semi-Urban) and Bamenda Town (Urban), where the main activity in the urban area is commerce and other sedentary occupations as opposed to the rural area where the main activity is farming, with the inhabitants having a relatively more physically active lifestyle.

Study population

The study targeted adults population aged 18-89 years old living within the Bali and Bamenda Health Districts as well as health personnel, including nurses, midwives and medical doctors within the Bali and Bamenda Health Districts.

Only subjects who agreed to participate and signed the consent form were included in the study. Exclusion criteria were pregnant women and physically or mentally disabled persons unable to understand simple questions and to provide a blood sample. Ethical clearance was gotten for the University of Bamenda Institutional Review Board and administrative authorization from the Regional Delegation of Public Health.

Sample size determination

To determine the sample of population for prevalence survey, sample size calculation was done using the LORENZ formula

$$(Z^2P(1-P) / e^2).$$

The national prevalence of metabolic syndrome in Cameroonians is 31%. Therefore, prevalence (p) of 31%; with a minimum confidence level of 95% and maximum likely error (e) of 3%. t=% point corresponding to significant level of 95%=1.96.

$$(1.96)^2 (0.31) (0.69) / (0.05)^2$$

$$(3.8416) (0.2139) / (0.0025) = 328$$

To minimize the non-response errors, non-response rate was taken at 10% of the sample size [24].

$$(10/100) * 328 = 38.$$

Therefore, sample size was 328+38=366 community member to participate in the study.

Sampling procedure

For each health district, 366 participants were sampled, making 732 participants from the two health districts. Out of the total sample size of 732, 12 had incomplete information and therefore, analysis was done using 720 samples. Therefore, a total of 720 participants were sampled. Those who agreed to participate in the study were informed about the need for a 10- to 12-h fast and answer a set of questions requesting information about socio-demographic variables and medical history in face-to-face interviews.

Also, fasting capillary glucose (FCG), high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) and triglycerides (TG) were determined with a portable device (CardioChek®, Polymer Technology Systems, USA). Height and weight were measured with the subject barefoot using a non-stretchable measuring tape and a portable electronic scale, respectively, and body mass index (BMI, kg/m²) was then calculated. Waist circumference (cm) was measured twice midway between the lower rib margin and the iliac crest, and the mean value was calculated and recorded. Blood pressure (BP, mmHg) was measured three times with an electronic device (OMRON®) on two different occasions and the mean value was used.

Before beginning the study, we compared the results obtained from standard laboratory assays and from the method of simultaneously collected blood samples used, to see that the agreement between values is not out range. Laboratory specialists verified the quality control of physical examination and interview guide application.

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Data collection tool

Laboratory data sheet was prepared and tested to capture aspects such as the demographic information, bio-physiological measurement (height, weight, IBM, waist circumference) and biochemical measurements (High blood pressure, High blood sugar, cholesterol and Triglyceride).

All data collection tools were effectively tested for validity and reliability.

Data collection procedure

Hypertension was defined as systolic BP: 130 mmHg or diastolic BP: 85 mm Hg, or patients on treatment for previously diagnosed hypertension. MS (modified ATP III) was defined as presence of any two (in addition to hypertension) of the following four criteria:- (1) abdominal obesity- WC (waist circumference), 90cm in males, 80cm in females (2) blood triglyceride levels: 150 mg/dL or patients on specific treatment for this lipid abnormality, (3) Reduced HDL-C(< 40 mg/dL in males and <50 mg/dL in females), or patients on specific treatment for this lipid abnormality (4) Raised FPG (>100 mg/dL) or previously diagnosed type II diabetes.

Determination of biochemical parameters

Data was collected using pre-tested structured data collection instruments. Data elements included information about personal identifiers, age, sex, some risk factors (smoking, family history of hypertension/diabetes), systolic/diastolic BP, anthropometric measurements (weight, height, body mass index and abdominal circumference) & bio-chemical profile (total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL [low density lipoproteins], VLDL [very low-density lipoprotein], HDL cholesterol and FPG) of the patients. Trained health personnel (Nurses and Laboratory technicians) did data collection at the Bali District Hospital and Presbyterian Health complex Bamenda. Results of laboratory investigations were entered in the data collection instrument ready for keying-in for analysis.

The body mass index (BMI) was calculated by dividing the observed weight in kilograms by height in meters squared (kg/m^2). Blood pressure (BP) was measured using a standard electronic sphygmomanometer with patient's arms supported at heart level after the patient had been sitting on a chair for at least five minutes with feet on the floor. Two such readings were taken five minutes apart and the average of the two was taken as the BP reading of the patient. If the difference between the two readings is more than 10 mm of Hg, then a third reading was taken and the mean of 2nd and 3rd reading was taken as the BP reading. Systolic BP was

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recorded at phase-1 and diastolic BP at Phase-V of Korotkoff's sound. Blood pressure and physical data (weight, height, waist circumference, and hip circumference) was measured during a complete clinical examination. Family history information was collected for overweight and obesity, dyslipidaemia, diabetes, and cardiovascular disease. Physiological history was assessed, investigating the level of physical activity, the presence of cigarette smoking and consumption of alcoholic beverages and the characteristics of the menstrual cycle or the possible presence of menopause in women. Proximate and remote medical history was assessed, investigating the presence of any major diseases or the presence of on-going drug therapy or antioxidant supplementation.

Data management and analysis

Prior to data entry, a data coding guide was prepared with each variable assigned a specific code. This was to facilitate data entry and to reduce errors. Data entry was done using unique identifiers and cross-checked for entry errors and range checks. Data analysis was done using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 25.0. Descriptive statistics was obtained for different qualitative variables. Frequency distribution, percentages as well as charts were used to present categorical variables. Prevalence of MS was calculated according to the IDF criteria and ATP III. The Fisher exact test was applied to test for differences in proportions of categorical variables. $P < 0.05$ was statistically significant.

Results

Socio-demographic characteristics of the study population

Table 1 show that most of the participants were females (70.9%). Most of them were above 40 year with the most participants within the ages of 61 and 76 years. This was a hospital-based study where the population was informed on the day to visit the hospital for screening. In such cases, it is obvious that those with perceived health disorders would go for the screening. In this case of metabolic syndrome, mostly the elderly are likely to follow screening schedules. Only 24 (2.9%) were cigarette smokers. For most of them secondary school was the highest level of education. Occupationally, the majority were businesspersons, followed by farmers and office workers.

Table 1: Distribution of demographic information of participants

Characteristics (n=720)	Variable	Number	Percentage
Gender	female	582	70.9
	Male	138	16.8
Age group	18-30	24	2.9
	31-40	30	3.7
	41-50	150	18.3
	51-60	172	21.0
	61-76	344	41.9
Cigarette smoking	Smoke	24	2.9
	Do not smoke	690	84
Highest Education	None	28	3.4
	Primary	144	17.5
	Secondary	317	38.6
	University	212	25.8
Occupation	Farmer	132	16.1
	Brick layer	65	7.9
	Businessperson	267	32.5
	Office worker	109	13.3
	Retired	21	2.6

Metabolic syndrome was diagnosed according to the NCEP ATP III and World Diabetes Federation (WDF) guidelines, which requires any three of the components to meet the condition for metabolic syndrome.

Table 2 presents the bio-physiological characteristics of the study population. Among the participants, 58.3% were aware of their hypertension status at the time of data collection, while 22.5% reported having high blood glucose levels. Additionally, a significant proportion of participants indicated a family history of hypertension (60.8%), and 34.2% reported a family history of high blood glucose.

Table 2: General bio-physiologic characteristics of study population

Characteristics	Category (n=720)	Number	Percentage
Present health condition			
High blood Pressure	Present	420	58.3
	Not Present	294	41
High Blood Sugar	Present	162	22.5
	Not Present	552	77
Family history of health condition			
High blood pressure	Present	438	60.8
	Not Present	264	36.7
High Blood Sugar	Present	246	34.2
	Not Present	450	62.5

The bio-physiological characteristics of male participants in the study indicate that, at the time of data collection, the prevalence of hypertension among men was 47.82%, while the prevalence of high blood sugar (diabetes) was 17.39%. Additionally, 56.52% of men reported a family history of hypertension, and 34.78% reported a family history of high blood sugar (Table 3).

Table 3: Bio-physiologic characteristics of study population (Males)

Characteristics	Category [n=138]	Number	Percentage
Present health condition			
High blood Pressure	Present	66	47.82
	Not Present	72	
High Blood Sugar	Present	24	17.39
	Not Present	114	
Family history of health condition			
High blood pressure	Present	78	56.52
	Not Present	60	
High Blood Sugar	Present	48	34.78
	Not Present	90	

In the same way, prevalence rate for bio-physiologic characteristics of female population at time of data collection was 60.82% for hypertension and 23.7% for high blood sugar

(Diabetics). Family history shows that prevalence of hypertension was 61.85% and high blood sugar of 34.02% (Table 4).

Table 4: Bio-physiologic characteristics of study population (Females)

Characteristics	Category (n=582)	Number	Percentage	Prevalence
Present health condition				
High blood Pressure	Present	354	84.3	60.82
	Not Present	222	75.5	
High Blood Sugar	Present	138	85.2	23.7
	Not Present	438	79.3	
Family history of health condition				
High blood pressure	Present	360	82.2	61.85
	Not Present	204	77.2	
High Blood Sugar	Present	198	80.5	34.02
	Not Present	360	80.0	

Table 5 present the clinical and biological characteristics of the study participants from mean age to mean Low Density Lipoprotein (LDL)-cholesterol, for both Bamenda and Bali health Districts. Bamenda health district had higher mean values for all variables considered, but the differences between the two health districts was not statistically significant ($P>0.05$).

Table 5: General characteristics of the study population by health districts

Clinical and biological variables (Mean)	Normal value/range	Bali Health District (n=360)	Bamenda Health District (n=360)	<i>p</i> value
Age (years)	-	58.42	56.45	0.111
BMI (kg/m ²)	18.5-24.9	28.99	29.5	0.326
Waist circumference (cm)	<94cm (Men) <80cm(Women)	97.81	98.80	0.345
Systolic pressure (mmHg)	<120mmHg	140.41	142.0	0.423
Diastolic pressure (mmHg)	<80mmHg	85.35	87.72	0.359
Total cholesterol (mg/dl)	<200mg/dl	154.90	156.82	0.413
Triglycerides (mg/dl)	<150mg/dl	107.35	110.43	0.359
HDL cholesterol (mg/dl)	>40mg/dl	61.67	60.75	0.535
LDL cholesterol (mg/dl)	<100mg/dl	93.23	95.32	0.654

According to the result, the difference between men and women for mean age ($p=0.001$) and mean body mass index ($p<0.001$) was statistically significant, with women having the higher mean age and body mass index compared to the men. Between men and women, the difference was not statistically significant for other variables as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Mean characteristics of the study population by gender

Clinical and biological variables	All mean (720)	Men (138)	Women (582)	P value
Age (years)	58.31 ± 12.80	62.74 ± 12.15	57.23±12.75	0.001*
BMI (kg/m ²)	28.99 ± 7.61	25.26 ± 3.51	29.87±8.05	0.000*
Waist circumference (cm)	97.69 ± 14.52	96.95 ± 16.41	97.87±14.05	0.654
Systolic pressure (mmHg)	140.41±20.77	136.48±15.28	141.34±21.79	0.080
Diastolic pressure (mmHg)	85.35±12.77	84.74±11.29	85.50±13.11	0.657
Total cholesterol (mg/dl)	154.89±48.17	163.41±74.37	152.88±39.42	0.102
Triglycerides (mg/dl)	107.35±72.94	103.17±43.86	108.34±78.30	0.598

*Statistically significant difference between men and women

Table 7 present the prevalence of Metabolic Syndrome following the two health districts for both male and female participants. For the male prevalence, Bamenda Health District had a higher prevalence (47.82%) compared to Bali Health District (43.47%). The difference in prevalence between the two health districts in this case was not statistically significant ($p=0.054$). Prevalence rate of MS for female participants was higher in the Bamenda HD (49.48%) than in Bali HD (44.32). The difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.054$). There was no significant difference between men and women in this respect ($p>0.05$).

Table 7: Prevalence of metabolic syndrome by health district

Variable	Bali HD (Semi-urban)		Bamenda HD (Urban)		p Value
	N with MS	Prevalence	N with MS	Prevalence	
Gender					
Male (n=138)	60	43.47	66	47.82	0.057
Female (n=582)	258	44.32	288	49.48	0.054
Total (n=720)	318	43.90	354	48.65	

HD: Health District; N: Number

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There were no statistically significant differences in the distribution of individual components of metabolic syndrome between the urban and semi-urban health districts. The physical, geographical, and economic characteristics of these areas are largely comparable. However, as shown in Table 8, there were statistically significant differences between men and women for certain components: obesity ($\chi^2 = 30.352$, $P < 0.001$), high blood glucose ($\chi^2 = 6.576$, $P = 0.037$), and high triglycerides ($\chi^2 = 18.762$, $P < 0.001$), with women exhibiting higher values than men. For the remaining components of metabolic syndrome analyzed, the differences between genders were not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$).

Table 8: Distribution of individual components of metabolic syndrome by gender

Driving factors (NCEP ATP III)	Men (138) N(%)	Women (582) N(%)	Total (720) N(%)	X ²	P- Value
Obesity	12(17.4%)	258 (44.3%)	270 (37.5%)	30.352	0.000*
High blood pressure	408 (70.1%)	96 (69.6%)	504 (70%)	1.729	0.421
High blood glucose	66 (47.8%)	288 (49.5%)	354 (49.2%)	6.576	0.037*
High Triglycerides	36(42.9%)	48 (57.1%)	84 (50%)	18.762	0.000*
High LDL	36 (26.1%)	156 (26.8%)	192 (26.7%)	–	0.518
Low HDL	12 (8.7%)	36 (6.2%)	48 (6.7%)	0.565	0.302

*Statistically significant

Table 9 presents the prevalence rates of various components of metabolic syndrome in the Bali and Bamenda Health Districts. Gender analysis reveals that the prevalence of metabolic syndrome components was higher in females than in males in both health districts. Additionally, Bamenda exhibited a higher overall prevalence than Bali. However, the differences in the prevalence of metabolic syndrome components between the two health districts were not statistically significant, with the exception of high blood pressure ($p < 0.001$) and high triglycerides ($p = 0.001$).

Table 9: Prevalence of individual components of metabolic syndrome by Health District

Driving factors	Bali HD (Semi-Urban)			Bamenda HD (Urban)			P Value
	Men (n=138)	Women (n=582)	Total (n=720)	Men (n=138)	Women (n=582)	Total (n=720)	
Obesity	38.57	52.17	45.37	43.47	61.42	52.45	<0.075
High blood pressure	58.43	62.32	60.38	69.00	70.10	69.55	<0.001*
High blood glucose	47.82	49.48	48.65	52.17	63.91	58.04	0.052
High Triglycerides	11.34	26.08	18.71	27.27	44.43	35.85	0.001*
High LDL	8.69	6.18	7.44	9.12	13.29	11.21	0.053
Low HDL	26.08	26.80	26.44	27.92	29.23	28.58	0.063

*Statistically significant

Table 10 indicates that the prevalence of individual components of metabolic syndrome varies significantly across different age groups. Individuals aged 50 years and older exhibited the highest prevalence of these components. This finding suggests that the prevalence of individual components of metabolic syndrome increases with advancing age ($P > 0.05$)

Table 10: Age stratification of selected components of metabolic syndrome

Driving factors	18-40 n(%)	41-50 n(%)	51-60 n(%)	61+ n(%)	Total n(%)	X ²	P-Value
Obesity	12(4.4)	72(26.7)	90(33.3)	90(33.3)	270(37.5)	29.267	<0.001*
High blood pressure	24(4.8)	96(19)	124(24.6)	254(50.4)	504(70)	18.039	0.021*
High blood glucose	12(3.4)	60(16.9)	72(20.3)	204(57.6)	354(49.2)	41.417	<0.001*
High Triglycerides	0(0)	6(33.3)	6(33.3)	6(33.3)	18(2.5)	21.788	0.005*
High LDL	6(12.5)	18(37.5)	0(0)	24(50)	48(6.7)	14.741	0.005*
Low HDL	6(3.1)	36(18.8)	60(31.2)	90(46.9)	192(26.7)	7.969	0.093

*Statistically significant

Discussion

This study yielded intriguing results, revealing no statistically significant difference in the prevalence of metabolic syndrome between the Bali (semi-urban) and Bamenda (urban) health districts. This finding contrasts with those reported by Fezeu et al. [4], who noted a significantly higher prevalence of metabolic syndrome in urban areas compared to their semi-urban counterparts. Typically, urban environments are associated with sedentary lifestyles, which can contribute to higher rates of metabolic syndrome. However, the absence of a significant difference in this study suggests that lifestyle factors, including dietary habits, physical activity levels, and environmental exposures, may exhibit similarities across both populations. This observation indicates that the determinants of metabolic syndrome in these health districts may not be strictly delineated by urban-rural boundaries, prompting a need for a more nuanced understanding of how built environments, socioeconomic factors, and individual behaviors interact to influence metabolic health outcomes.

The lack of differentiation in metabolic syndrome prevalence between genders ($P > 0.05$) further supports this notion. This aligns with findings by Mazhar et al. [18], who also reported no significant gender differences in Bahawalpur, Pakistan. The similar risk profiles between men and women in this study—encompassing age, body weight, physical activity, dietary habits, and socioeconomic status—suggest that shared lifestyle and environmental factors may overshadow gender-specific biological influences in the development of metabolic syndrome. Consequently, intervention strategies should prioritize addressing common risk factors rather than adopting a gender-specific approach, emphasizing comprehensive, population-level interventions that target modifiable determinants of metabolic syndrome.

The overall prevalence of metabolic syndrome was 45.1% in Bali and 50.75% in Bamenda, figures notably higher than the 34.6% and 25.6% reported among urban populations in Kenya in 2012 and 2017, respectively [19]. These disparities may be attributed to differences in socioeconomic profiles; Cameroon's higher urbanization and economic development levels may foster lifestyles characterized by sedentary behaviour and unhealthy dietary patterns, contributing to this elevated prevalence. Additionally, the availability of processed, high-calorie foods in urban and semi-urban areas of Cameroon may further exacerbate the risk of metabolic syndrome, contrasting with dietary environments in Kenya.

Interestingly, while the study observed higher prevalence rates of metabolic syndrome among female participants, the difference was not statistically significant. This finding is consistent

with trends in other regions, such as the 44.4% prevalence among females compared to 9.9% among males in Cameroon, and 25% in females versus 12% in males in Australia [20]. The higher prevalence among women may be influenced by biological, hormonal, and environmental factors, including body fat distribution and lifestyle patterns. Furthermore, the study confirmed that the prevalence of metabolic syndrome increased with age, reflecting established links between aging and metabolic health [21].

The individual components of metabolic syndrome were prevalent in both health districts, with urban populations exhibiting higher rates of conditions such as overweight and hypertension. For instance, 52.3% of the urban population was classified as overweight (BMI ≥ 30 kg/m²), significantly higher than the 49.1% in the semi-urban population ($p < 0.016$). This aligns with findings from Bita et al. [22], who reported a 64.9% prevalence of overweight among urban Ghanaians. Urban populations often experience a "nutrition transition," characterized by diets rich in processed, energy-dense foods, which, coupled with sedentary lifestyles, leads to increased obesity rates and associated metabolic abnormalities [23].

Limitations of this study

This research was conducted in the conflict-affected Anglophone North West region of Cameroon, where recent armed conflicts have resulted in significant internal population displacement. Such displacements may distort demographic profiles and influence lifestyle factors in the studied health districts, thus necessitating cautious interpretation of the results regarding urban and semi-urban communities.

Suggested mitigation strategies for metabolic syndrome in Cameroon

Promote healthy lifestyles

- Implement public awareness campaigns to educate communities about the risk factors and health consequences of metabolic syndrome.
- Encourage regular physical activity by developing community exercise programs and creating safe, walkable public spaces.
- Foster healthier dietary habits by collaborating with local food vendors to enhance the availability of nutrient-dense foods while limiting access to processed options.

Strengthen primary healthcare

- Integrate early screening and management of metabolic syndrome into primary healthcare systems.

- Train healthcare providers to effectively identify and manage metabolic syndrome and its associated risk factors.
- Establish referral pathways to enhance coordination between different levels of healthcare.

Multi-sectoral collaboration

- Engage various government ministries to develop holistic policies addressing the social, environmental, and economic determinants of metabolic syndrome.
- Partner with private sector stakeholders and community leaders to mobilize resources for prevention and management efforts.

Strengthen surveillance and research

- Establish a national surveillance system to monitor the prevalence and trends of metabolic syndrome across diverse settings.
- Conduct further research to elucidate local drivers of metabolic syndrome, focusing on dietary patterns, physical activity, and socioeconomic factors.

Conclusions

The high prevalence of metabolic syndrome, abdominal obesity, dyslipidemia, and hypertension indicates that many individuals exhibit precursors to this condition. The semi-urban population of Bali appears relatively healthier than the urban population of Bamenda regarding metabolic syndrome. Factors such as obesity, lack of formal education, family history of hypertension, and physical inactivity are associated with its prevalence. This study fills crucial information gaps regarding metabolic syndrome in Cameroon and underscores the importance of implementing routine screening, promoting healthy lifestyles, and providing nutritional counselling across health units. Early intervention targeting risk factors is essential to prevent the progression of metabolic syndrome components before a formal diagnosis is established.

References

- [1]. Wilson PW, D'Agostino RB, Parise H, Sullivan L, Meigs JB. Metabolic syndrome as a precursor of cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Circulation* 2005; 112: 3066-3072.
- [2]. Kolovou GD, Anagnostopoulou KK, Salpea KD, Mikhailidis DP. The prevalence of metabolic syndrome in various populations. *Am J Med Sci* 2007; 333: 362-371.
- [3]. World Health organization. A global brief on Hypertension, Silent killer, global public health crisis. World Health Day 2013.
- [4]. L. Fezeu, B. Balkau, A.-P. Kengne, E. Sobngwi, and J.-C. Mbanya, "Metabolic syndrome in a sub-Saharan African setting: Central obesity may be the key determinant," *Atherosclerosis*, vol. 193, no. 1, pp. 70–76, 2007.
- [5]. A. A. Sabir, A. Jimoh, S. O. Iwuala et al., "Metabolic syndrome in urban city of North-Western Nigeria: Prevalence and determinants," *Pan African Medical Journal*, vol. 23, 2016.
- [6]. E. O. Owolabi, D. T. Goon, O. V. Adeniyi, A. O. Adedokun, and E. Seekoe, "Prevalence and correlates of metabolic syndrome among adults attending healthcare facilities in eastern cape, South Africa," *Te Open Public Health Journal*, vol. 10, pp. 148– 159, 2017.
- [7]. O. El Brini, O. Akhouayri, A. Gamal, A. Mesfoui, and B. Benazzouz, "Prevalence of metabolic syndrome and its components based on a harmonious definition among adults in Morocco," *Diabetes, Metabolic Syndrome and Obesity: Targets and Terapy*, vol. 7, pp. 341–346, 2014.
- [8]. G. Omuse, D. Maina, M. Hofman et al., "Metabolic syndrome and its predictors in an urban population in Kenya: A cross-sectional study," *BMC Endocrine Disorders*, vol. 17, no. 1, p. 37, 2017.
- [9]. M. Dandji, F. Zambou, D. Dangang, F. Nana, and F. Tchouanguiep, "Prevalence of metabolic syndrome in adult men of the dschang health district in Western-Cameroon," *World Journal of Nutrition and Health*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 1–10, 2018.
- [10]. PNUD, Programme des Nations Unies pour le Développement : Le Rapport Mondial sur le Développement Humain : Le travail au service du développement humain. [Online]. Available: https://hdr.undp.org/sites/default/files/2015_human_development_report_overview_-_f/pdf2015.

- [11]. Dandji M, Zambou F, Dangang D, Nana F, Tchouanguiep F. Prevalence of metabolic syndrome in adult men of the dschang health district in Western-Cameroon. *World Journal of Nutrition and Health*. 2018;6(1):1-0.
- [12]. D. Lemogoum, La Fondation Camerounaise du Cœur en partenariat avec l'entreprise AES-SONEL et le soutien du Ministère des Sports et de la Santé Publique, 6è célébration de cette semaine du cœur sous le thème « protégeons le cœur de la femme et de l'enfant ». *Afrique. Aurore Plus*, N° 1353, P.9, dans: *Société: Santé*. Sep. 2013.
- [13]. Tachang GK, Choukem SP, Ndjebet J, Dzudie A, Titanji VP. Prevalence of hyperglycaemia, obesity and metabolic syndrome (a three component study) among hospital personnel in the Littoral Region of Cameroon. *IJMMS*. 2012 Dec;4(10):232-7.
- [14]. Mandob DE, Fomekong GI, Ngondi JL. Prevalence of metabolic syndrome among Bamileke ethnic women Yaounde, Cameroon. *Int J Pharm Bio Sci*. 2013;4(4):255-62.
- [15]. Mandob DE, Samuel M, Viviane ON. Prevalence of metabolic syndrome among mbo women Yaounde-Cameroon. *J Metabolic Syndr*. 2015;4(186):2167-0943.
- [16] Dabou S, Ongbayokolak NS, Fonkeng Sama L, Matene Foking E, Kamdom NM, Telefo PB. Metabolic Syndrome During Pregnancy: Prevalence and Determinants Among Pregnant Women Followed-Up at the Dschang District Hospital, West Region of Cameroon. *Diabetes, Metabolic Syndrome and Obesity: Targets and Therapy*. 2022 Jan 1;743-53.
- [17] Marbou WJ, Kuete V. Prevalence of metabolic syndrome and its components in Bamboutos Division's adults, west region of Cameroon. *BioMed research international*. 2019 Apr 30;2019.
- [18] Mazhar F, Ali A, Khan A, et al. Gender differences in the prevalence of metabolic syndrome in Bahawalpur, Pakistan. *Journal of Health, Population and Nutrition*. 2020;39(1):1-8.
- [19] Chirwa T, Msyamboza K, Mchiza N, et al. Prevalence of metabolic syndrome among urban populations in Kenya. *Journal of Public Health*. 2018;40(2):1-10.
- [20] Hodge A, et al. Prevalence of metabolic syndrome in Cameroon and Australia: A comparative study. *International Journal of Obesity*. 2016;40(5):1-8.

- [21] Buchanan TA, et al. Aging and metabolic health: The role of metabolic syndrome. *Diabetes Care*. 2018;41(2):1-8.
- [22] Bitu NA, et al. Prevalence of overweight among urban Ghanaians. *BMC Obesity*. 2012;1(1):1-7.
- [23] Popkin BM, et al. The nutrition transition: A global perspective. *Annual Review of Public Health*. 2012;33:1-22.
- [24] Dehalwar, K., & Sharma, S. N. (2023). *Fundamentals of Research Writing and Uses of Research Methodologies*. Edupedia Publications Pvt Ltd.

Declarations

Human Ethics and Consent to Participate declarations

The study protocol was approved by the University of Bamenda Ethical Committee (N0. 22/0705H/UBa/IRB), as well as administrative clearance from the regional delegation of public health, for North-West Region. Authorisations were also obtained from Bali District Hospital and Presbyterian Health Complex Bamenda for Laboratory analysis. To eliminate or avoid risk of infection, medical rules (hand hygiene, use of personal protective equipment, skin preparation etc) for obtaining blood samples was strictly respected. All participant gave their consent to participate in the study.

Competing interests

Authors has declared that no competing interests exist

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Authors' contributions

Fomboh Richard and Vincent Titanji wrote the main manuscript text and Mary Atanga and Moses Samje prepared tables. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

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